

Building the Legal Knowledge Graph for Smart Compliance Services in Multilingual Europe

Welcome to Issue #1 of the **Lynx Newsletter!** The main objective of Lynx is to create an **ecosystem of smart cloud services to better manage compliance, based on a Legal Knowledge Graph (LKG)** which integrates and links heterogeneous compliance data sources including legislation, case law, standards and other private contracts.

Lynx will provide more effective ways of accessing huge amounts of digital regulatory compliance documents, including legislation, case law, standards, industry norms and best practices. In particular, this solution envisages an ecosystem of smart cloud services to better manage compliance documents, based on a Legal Knowledge Graph, which integrates and links heterogeneous compliance data sources.

This ecosystem will enable **smart search, smart assistance and smart referencing** of case law, as well as Artificial Intelligence technologies and machine translation of regulatory compliance documents. Lynx will offer a legal knowledge and information one-stop shop service for SMEs and other operating internationally.

In this newsletter you will find news and events related to the Lynx project, such as, updates on release of new content in the Lynx home page data portal, achievements, meetings and other public information. You can also check the project's website at <http://lynx-project.eu>.

Lynx consortium

The Lynx consortium comprises partners with complementary profiles that are fully committed to the project, have world-wide expertise in their fields of activities and have the capacity and the resources to fulfil the ambitious project objectives.

The consortium includes technological partners ([UPM](#), [SWC](#), [DFKI](#), [TILDE](#), [ALP](#), [KD](#)) with long experience in areas such as language technologies, knowledge management, Semantic Web, and complex systems integration, which are core in the technological solutions devised to attain the Lynx goals. Their areas of expertise are complementary and synergies among some of them have been already successfully exploited in past projects such as LIDER, FREME or LDL4HELTA.

Some of the partners ([KD](#), [OLS](#), [DNV](#)) are also data providers. Their data, both domain independent and specific of the legal domain, will serve as input to the data value chain since the very beginning, in addition to other data sources from third parties.

Experts in the legal domain are also present in the project ([UAB](#), [OLS](#), [CC](#)) to ensure that the particularities of the legal and regulatory data are well understood. They will also allow the consortium to better interpret the user compliance requirements during the analysis phase, and will be essential to validate the compliance services developed in Lynx.

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Search data

Statistics

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datasets

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organizations

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groups

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This website is maintained by the H2020 Lynx project

Lynx Data Portal

The Lynx Data Portal is now online at <http://data.lynx-project.eu/> This Data Portal contains more than 60 datasets from [OEG](#) and [TILDE](#). In these datasets you can find Lynx labour law termlist, e-Compliance multilingual thesaurus, Spanish Labour Law corpus, and others.

Click the button below and check out the Lynx Data Portal!!

[Go to Lynx Data Portal](#)

Lynx partner co-organising a workshop at ISWC 2019

Auckland 2019 ISWC

Good news! The workshop proposal sent to ISWC 2019, co-organised by [Elena Montiel-Ponsoda](#), Lynx partner from UPM, has been accepted!

The workshop is called [International Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Big Data Technologies for Legal Documents \(AI4LEGAL\)](#) and it is also being co-organised by [Manolis Koubarakis](#) (University of Athens), [Grigoris Antoniou](#) (University of Huddersfield), [Guido Governatori](#) (Data 61 CSIRO) and [Yoshinobu Kano](#) (Shizuoka University).

AI4LEGAL will be held during the [International Semantic Web Conference](#) (26th-30th October 2019) in Auckland, New Zealand. See [website](#) for more details.

[Go to Workshop Home Page](#)

Lynx Coding Sprint took place in Cercedilla

During the "Coding spring week", several collaborators of the Lynx initiative stayed at [UPM's facilities in Cercedilla](#) to work in the different packages of the project.

Representatives of [SWC](#), [OLS](#), [DFKI](#), [Tilde](#), [KD](#), [ALP](#), [UNIZAR](#) and [UPM](#) joined efforts to take the most of these days and reach consistent results.

[Read more](#)

2nd-6th June, 2019

European Semantic Web Conference

Lynx partners have submitted a paper to the European Semantic Conference (ESWC) that will be held in Slovenia and it has been accepted.

Title: Question Answering for Link Prediction and Verification.

Description: We tackle the problem of knowledge graph population with the help of question answering system. The proposed workflow is the following: ask questions over noisy texts, verify the answers and expand knowledge graphs with new data automatically. Following recent success of Question Answering systems in outperforming humans, we employ the developed tools to identify and verify new links. To identify the gaps in a knowledge graph, we use the existing techniques and combine them with Question Answering tools to extract concealed knowledge. We outline the overall procedure and discuss preliminary results.

Workshop on Natural Legal

Language Processing (NLLP)

Lynx partners submitted a paper to the Workshop on [Natural Legal Language Processing \(NLLP\)](#) co-located with [NAACL 2019](#) in Minneapolis, Minnesota, USA. This work has been accepted for presentation at the workshop.

Title: Developing and Orchestrating a Portfolio of Natural Legal Language Processing and Document Curation Services

Description: The paper describes the Lynx approach to the processing of legal on a high level. We present a portfolio of natural legal language processing and document curation services currently under development in a collaborative European project. First, we give an overview of the project and the different use cases, while, in the main part of the article, we focus upon the 13 different processing services that are being deployed in different prototype applications using a flexible and scalable microservices architecture. Their orchestration is operationalised using a content and document curation workflow manager.

CODEX
The Stanford Center for Legal Informatics

Lynx presented to CodeX, the Stanford Legal Tech Group

[CodeX, the Stanford Group of Legal Informatics](#), attended the [IRIS conference](#) that takes place in Salzburg, during the 21st - 23rd of February.

Partners of Lynx Consortium presented the project to this group on Thursday 21st.

[Read more](#)

2nd Workshop on Technologies for Regulatory Compliance

The Lynx project is based on a very simple idea: the critical mass of legal open data on the web has been reached and if duly collected, analysed and interlinked as a Legal Knowledge Graph, it will be ready to enable a new breed of multilingual services for compliance. Thus the areas of interest in this workshop are three:

- theoretical foundations and the legal regulatory framework towards compliance in Europe;
- the semantic web technologies which support the legal knowledge graph and
- language technologies used to bridge the idiomatic barrier that hampers the commerce of products and services in Europe

Workshop within the [31st International Conference on Legal Knowledge and Information Systems \(JURIX\)](#), hosted by the Faculty of Law and the department of Artificial Intelligence in the Bernoulli Institute of Mathematics, Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence, Faculty of Science and Engineering of the University of Groningen.

[Go to TEREKOM 2018 Proceedings](#)

H2020 Lynx Project

@lynxH2020

Thank you @Cuatrecasas for the organization of the 4th Lynx Plenary Meeting in #Barcelona Amazing work during the p...

<https://t.co/9tdt8OSqjZ>

11:03 AM - Apr 30, 2019

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See lynxH2020's other Tweets

Consortium

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 780602

**H2020 Lynx Project - Grant Agreement no.
780602**

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